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Dispersion and functionalization of nanoparticles synthesized by gas aggregation source: Opening new routes towards the fabrication of nanoparticles for bio-medicine

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Abstract

The need to find new nanoparticles for biomedical applications is pushing the limits of the fabrication methods. New techniques with versatilities beyond the extended chemical routes can provide new insight in the field. In particular gas aggregation sources offer the possibility to fabricate nanoparticles with controlled size, composition and structure out of thermodynamics. In this context, the milestone is the optimization of the dispersion and functionalization processes of nanoparticles once fabricated by these routes as they are generated in the gas phase and deposited on substrates in vacuum or ultra-high vacuum conditions. In the present work we propose a fabrication route in ultra-high vacuum that is compatible with the subsequent dispersion and functionalization of nanoparticles in aqueous media and, that is more remarkable, in one single step. In particular, we will present the fabrication of nanoparticles with a sputter gas aggregation source, using a Fe₅₀B₅₀ target, and their further dispersion and functionalization with polyethyleneglycol (PEG). A characterization of these nanoparticles is carried out before and after PEG functionalization. During functionalization, significant boron dissolution occurs, which facilitates nanoparticle dispersion in the aqueous solution. The use of different complementary techniques allows us to prove the PEG attachment onto the surface of the nanoparticles creating a shell to make them biocompatible. The result is the formation of nanoparticles with a structure mainly composed by a metallic Fe core and an iron oxide shell, surrounded by a second PEG shell dispersed in aqueous solution. Relaxivity measurements of these PEG functionalized nanoparticles assessed their effectiveness as contrast agents for Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) analysis. Therefore, this new fabrication route is a reliable alternative for the synthesis of nanoparticles for biomedicine.

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Author Contributions

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INTRODUCTION

Nanoparticles (NPs) have been extensively studied due to their great potential applications in many different fields. One of the most promising is their use in biomedicine¹⁻⁴. In particular, the development of new contrast agents for magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) contrast agent is being subject of several studies with the aim to enhance the sensibility of the technique for early detection of malign affections or monitoring of drug delivery^{5,6}.

There are two main types of contrast agents: paramagnetic compounds, which are based on Gadolinium complexes and mostly used as T_1 contrast agents since their effects are generally more notorious than in T_2 , and superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (SPIONs) which are mainly used as T_2 contrast agents⁷. The interest of SPIONs is primarily because of their low toxicity. However, these particles mainly accumulate in the liver and spleen reducing their effectiveness to image other organs⁸. Therefore, there is a need for alternative contrast agents, based on SPIONs, with altered biodistribution, to be able to assess other organs. Metals and metal alloys are excellent candidates from the magnetic viewpoint, although they may present toxicity problems. An adequate shell for a metallic core can be a good alternative to avoid toxicity and increase stability.

In this sense, core-shell structures lead to an improvement of NPs properties in many different aspects⁹. A metallic core providing high M_S (remaining superparamagnetic) surrounded by an oxide shell that provides chemical stability and lower toxicity can be an alternative to SPIONs. However the control of the oxidation in order to keep a metallic core for guidance purposes is still a limiting step concerning the fabrication of this kind of structures.

The synthesis of NPs for biomedical applications mainly follows chemical methods in solution (i.e.: co-precipitation, hydrothermal or sol-gel synthesis,...). The chemical methods present doubtless advantages of low cost and, usually, ease of fabrication. Physical methods offer reliable alternatives to fabricate NPs with controlled size, composition and structure. In particular, gas aggregation sources and more specifically sputter gas aggregation sources, such as Ion Cluster Sources (ICS) offer the possibility to fabricate NPs non obtainable by chemical routes with a precise control of the composition^{10,11} (i.e.: avoid oxidation of a particular element as it is an ultra-high vacuum, UHV, process), the structure^{12,13} and a narrow size distribution, that can be further improved by the use of a quadrupole mass filter¹¹. Hence, the gas aggregation sources open the possibility for the generation of new NPs that can be used for biomedical purposes. However, as the ICS is a high or ultra-high vacuum set-up, the fabricated NPs are first collected on a substrate and then extracted out of the vacuum chamber. Furthermore, in order to collect the amount of NPs needed for biomedical applications, multilayers of NPs are generated. Thanks to the soft landing of the nanoparticles fabricated by this technique, they are not deformed when deposited on the substrates^{10,14}. The subsequent dispersion of such multilayered NPs in aqueous solutions is not an easy task, as the adhesion of the NPs to the substrate and between them can be very strong in certain circumstances (especially when they are hydrophilic)¹⁵.

Our approach to provide alternative NPs that can be used as contrast agents consist in the fabrication of NPs by means of an ICS, using a Fe₅₀B₅₀ target. The first step to obtain metallic core - oxide shell structure was successfully accomplished and described in a previous study¹⁶. By using a Fe₅₀B₅₀ target, NPs with a metallic Fe core (~ 3 nm diameter, size extracted from the magnetic characterization) surrounded by a shell composed by a mixture of Fe and B oxides, hydroxides and oxynitrides were fabricated. The size of the NPs measured by TEM is 10.2 ± 2.4 nm, a size distribution narrow enough to present similar behaviour when exposed to a magnetic field. These NPs presented a superparamagnetic behaviour at room temperature (RT), which makes them appropriate candidates for biomedical applications. Their core-shell structure represents an inherent advantage for these applications, as the NPs with metallic core present an increased M_S as compared to fully oxidised ones, while the oxide shell makes these NPs stable when dispersed in aqueous solution avoiding the toxicity of the metallic core.

The second stage related to the dispersion and further functionalization of the NPs in order to make them biocompatible and suitable for biomedical applications is addressed in the present paper. Silva et al. previously synthesized Fe NPs using the same method in UHV and functionalized them with oleic acid. In their approach they covered the Si surface of the substrate with the oleic acid and further sonicated the deposit in toluene, followed by other steps (flocculation, centrifugation, decanting...)¹⁷. In our study we show that the introduction of B in the system, allows a direct and one step dispersion of the NPs in aqueous media. A characterization of the chemical and electronic structure of the NPs was carried out with the NPs deposited on solid substrates by means of X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) and Raman spectroscopy. Afterwards, UV-vis, Zeta potential and MRI experiments were carried out on the NPs dispersed in aqueous solution for the investigation of the effect of the PEG functionalization on the contrast enhancement.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Materials

Multilayers of NPs were fabricated using an Ion Cluster Source (ICS) from Oxford Applied Research Ltd.¹⁸ in ultra-high vacuum (UHV). A Fe₅₀B₅₀ target was used and a small N₂ flux was added to the sputtering gas (Ar). The NPs fabricated were deposited on naturally oxidized Si(100) wafers. Details of the fabrication conditions and their complete characterization can be found elsewhere¹⁶. The resulting NPs presented a mean size of 10.2 ± 2.4 nm according to TEM measurements. PEG functionalization of the NPs was carried out following two different approaches:

PEG functionalization of NPs deposited on Si(100)—The Si substrates with NPs were immersed in a stirred solution of PEG 400 2.5 mM for about 4 h at RT. After this process, the samples were thoroughly washed in ultrapure deionized water in order to remove the free PEG molecules and dried in an oven (in air) at 37 °C before any subsequent analysis. A scheme of the resulting system is depicted in figure 1a. A multilayer of NPs was left without functionalization for comparison purposes. From now on, these samples will be referred as *deposited Fe-B(O-N) NPs* and *functionalized PEG-Fe-B(O-N) NPs*.

PEG functionalization of dispersed NPs—The Si(100) substrates with NPs were immersed in 5 ml ultrapure deionized water and sonicated at RT to remove the NPs from the Si substrate. Then, 50 μl of PEG 400 were added to the solution with the NPs and the resulting solution was stirred for 4 h at RT. In order to remove the unbound PEG molecules, the solution was then centrifugated at 15000 rpm. The resulting NPs are schematized in figure 1b. In order to compare between unbounded and PEG bounded NPs in the same environment, two dispersions of NPs were prepared and the PEG solution was added only to one of them. From now on, the samples obtained from these solutions will be referred as *dispersed Fe-B(O-N) NPs* and *dispersed PEG-Fe-B(O-N) NPs*.

Experimental devices

The XPS measurements were performed using a SPECS PHOIBOS 100 spectrometer with MgK_{α} source (150 W, $h\nu = 1253.6$ eV) connected to an UHV analysis chamber with base pressure of 5×10^{-10} mbar. The absolute binding energies of the photoelectron spectra were determined by referencing to the C 1s transition at 285 eV (from adsorbed species). Surveys were measured with steps of 0.25 eV. High resolution spectra were measured within the spectral range of interest (± 20 eV around the core level emission peaks of interest), with 0.1 eV steps. Depth profile analysis was performed on the samples using Ar^+ ions at 1.4 keV. Analysis of the data was carried out with Casa XPS software¹⁹.

Raman spectra were acquired with a WITec Alpha 300 AR spectrometer at RT using an argon ion laser with an excitation wavelength of 531 nm and a spatial resolution of 300 nm.

UV-Vis analysis were performed on *dispersed Fe-B(O-N) and PEG-Fe-B(O-N) NPs* (0.30 mM solution). The absorption spectra were recorded using a Jasco V-670 UV-Vis-NIR spectrometer with a slit width of 2 nm and a spectral resolution of 1 nm. All the spectra were registered at RT in the wavenumber range of 190-900 nm.

The surface charge of *dispersed Fe-B(O-N) and PEG-Fe-B(O-N) NPs* were determined by zeta potential measurements. The analyses were carried out using a Zetasizer Nano ZS from Malvern equipped with a He-Ne laser (4 mW) working at 633 nm. Disposable capillary cells (DTS1061) were filled with 0.20 mM solution of dispersed NPs. Each sample was measured three times at 25 °C and an average value was calculated. All the data were registered and fitted using the equipment software.

Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) experiments were performed with a Bruker BioSpin MRI equipment PharmaScan equipped with a 7.0 Tesla magnet for pre-clinical studies on animal models, following the protocols suggested by the manufacturer. The NPs dispersed in a 0.30 mM solution were introduced in vertical position inside the radiofrequency (RF) volume coil 1 H RES 300 075/040 TR QSN, where T_2 weighted RARE (rapid acquisition with relaxation enhancement) MRI images were acquired in coronal section, which allows simultaneous viewing of different NPs concentrations and/or comparative uncoated and coated NPs analyses. All the measurements were carried out at RT. The parameters used for image acquisition were: RARE factor of 8, field of view (FOV) of 4×4 cm², matrix of 256×256 , repetition time (TR) of 2500 ms, echo time of 33 ms, TE effective of 56 ms. The values presented are the average of measurements on five different samples. The total

acquisition time for each scan was ~ 9 min. Images were processed using the Onis 2.4 software²⁰. The transverse relaxivity r_2 has been calculated using:

$$1/T_2=1/T_{20}+r_2C \quad (1)$$

where T_{20} is the transverse relaxation rate of the aqueous solution without NPs, and C is the concentration of NPs dispersed in the solution.

AFM measurements were carried out using the Cervantes AFM System from Nanotec Electronica S. L. The samples were measured in the dynamic mode using tips from Next-Tip S.L.²¹. Data processing was performed using the WSxM²² software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

NPs deposited on Si(100)

For a detailed chemical and structural characterization of the NPs with techniques like XPS or Raman, it is necessary to keep them deposited on solid surfaces. For this reason in this first section we present the characterization of the NPs deposited on Si(100) substrates.

Chemical characterization by XPS—A photoemission study was carried out comparing multilayers of *as deposited Fe-B(O-N) NPs* and *as functionalized Fe-B(O-N) NPs*. From the analysis of the survey scans (not shown here), it is observed that the same elements (B, C, N, O and Fe) are present in both systems, although their proportion is modified after functionalization. A clear evidence of PEG attachment during functionalization is the increase of the C content by 18%. In addition, there is a significant reduction of the proportion of B (~ 81%) and N (~ 67%).

For a better understanding of surface changes in terms of structure during the functionalization, high resolution spectra of the elements of interest were studied. In figure 2 we present the analysis of Fe 2p, B 1s, N 1s and O 1s core level spectra before and after functionalization. Detailed discussion concerning the assignation of the components is described elsewhere¹⁶. Each component plotted in a different colour represents a different species. The Fe 2p core level (figure 2a) was deconvoluted taking into account the existence of Fe^{2+} (709.5 eV) and Fe^{3+} (711.5 and 713.2 eV). No significant changes were found on the Fe 2p after PEG functionalization.

The analysis of the B 1s core level is displayed in figure 2b. Two components were identified in the spectra and assigned to sub-stoichiometric boron oxides and boron nitrides at 190.6 eV and 192.2 eV respectively. After PEG functionalization the intensity of both components decreased, although the reduction from sub-stoichiometric oxides is more pronounced (from a 9.7% of the global composition to a 1.4% after functionalization). As all nitrogen is in the form of boron oxynitride through N-O bonds (400 eV) and N-B bonds (398 eV)¹⁶, the decrease of boron content involves a diminution in the N content after functionalization as can be observed in the evolution of N 1s core level (figure 2c).

The analysis of the O 1s core level (figure 2d) exhibits the first evidences of PEG attachment. The *as deposited NPs* spectra displayed four contributions related to the presence of O-Fe bonds (530.3 eV); defective oxides and hydroxides (531.5 eV); O-B bonds (532.5 eV) and O-N bonds (533.7 eV). The relative proportion of these components is modified after PEG functionalization. The already reported reduction of B content produced not only a diminution in the relative proportion of O-B bonds (532.5 eV) but also of defective oxides in the system (531.5 eV), which is in agreement with the drastic decrease observed in the component at 192.2 eV of the B 1s core level (figure 2b). As a result, there is a relative increase of the stoichiometric Fe-O contribution. Apart from this, a new component at 532.8 eV is observed after functionalization. This component arises by the presence of PEG in the system²³. As this binding energy is close to the O-B contribution (532.5 eV), it is difficult to discern between both of them. However, considering the amount of B-O detected on the analysis of the B 1s core level, it is possible to estimate the total contribution of the B-O bonds to the O 1s spectra and, therefore, extract that PEG contribution to the O 1s core level is around 23%.

As an attempt to elucidate whether boron is totally dissolved during PEG functionalization or just from the NPs on top of the multilayer, a depth profile analysis was carried out until an approximate distance of 20 nm from the surface (the NPs present a mean size of 10 nm). The results are displayed in figure 3. The evolution of B and C concentration of a reference *as deposited NPs* sample is also displayed for comparison purposes (dashed lines). The B content of the *as functionalized NPs* increases from the 2% on the surface to 5% at 20 nm depth. In comparison, the reference *as deposited NPs* presented a boron content of around 11% at the surface of the multilayer and reach 20 % at 20 nm from the surface. This is a clear indication that B dissolution after the functionalization process affected more than one layer of NPs. B removal reduces the thickness of the NPs shell resulting in a relative larger Fe contribution after PEG functionalization (nearly three times larger than the *as deposited* sample¹⁶). The analysis of the Fe 2p core level at different depths evidenced a larger Fe⁰ contribution on the *as functionalized* sample (the Fe⁰ contribution in comparison to the *as deposited* sample displayed an increase close to 60% at 20 nm from the surface) because of this thinner shell. Apart from this, by comparing the evolution of the C content on the samples, there is a larger C contribution after PEG functionalization even at 20 nm from the surface, proving PEG attachment not only on top of the multilayer.

Structural characterization: Raman—A comparative Raman analysis between *as deposited* and *as functionalized Fe-B(O-N) NPs* was performed under an applied laser power of 0.14 mW. This low power was necessary to avoid structural phase transitions of NPs, which occur when exposed to higher laser powers levels. In previous Raman investigations of magnetic nanoparticles, Li et al. have already observed that laser irradiation induced phase transformation for laser powers higher than 0.35 mW²⁴. The present study required twice less power in order to avoid any phase transition. Figure 4 presents the Raman spectra of the samples. The Raman band for the silicon substrate was also included for comparison purposes. In addition, the most significant spectral features of iron/boron oxides/hydroxides and PEG are identified on the basis of the available published data²⁵⁻²⁸ and displayed at the bottom of figure 4. The *as deposited NPs* presented Raman modes at 366 cm⁻¹ and 684

cm^{-1} that can be assigned to iron oxide phases. Additionally, they present bands in the 1330 - 1630 cm^{-1} region that correspond to the superposition of iron and boron oxide phases. Finally, the Raman band close to 3000 cm^{-1} is characteristic of hydrocarbon contamination. From these results one can infer that Raman characterization of Fe-B oxide mixtures is not straightforward and only qualitative information can be extracted.

Raman analysis of the *as functionalized NPs* clearly evidenced bands at 690 cm^{-1} , 736 cm^{-1} and 1623 cm^{-1} characteristic of $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ and bands at 854 cm^{-1} , 1154 cm^{-1} , 1327 cm^{-1} , 1448 cm^{-1} , 1485 cm^{-1} , 2879 cm^{-1} and 2940 cm^{-1} characteristics of PEG. The stronger intensity of CH_2 groups in this sample is a clear evidence of PEG attachment to the *Fe-B(O-N)* NPs.

Up to now, the surface chemical analysis carried out on NPs deposited on Si(100) clearly revealed that B dissolution occurs on *Fe-B(O-N)* NPs during PEG functionalization. The boron is in the form of boron oxide and oxynitride¹⁶ and, according to our results, the B-O bond is the most affected by the dissolution. Hubacek et al. first reported the existence of a boron oxynitride and concluded that it was formed by two different phases: boron oxide and boron nitride²⁹. As boron oxide is soluble in water-based solutions but boron nitride is not, this could explain the observation of a preferential dissolution of the B-O phase. The proportion of B-N bonds in the NPs deposits is significantly smaller and the partial removal observed could be consequence of the dissolution of the surrounding B-O. Tokoro et al.³⁰ synthesized Fe NPs with a BN shell from mixed powders and reported the formation of a BN shell at 1573 K that totally prevents the oxidation of Fe cores. They claimed a catalytic effect of Fe for the BN formation. In our case, the fabrication is carried out at RT and some oxidation takes place when NPs are exposed to atmosphere, forming a boron oxide and an oxynitride. This means that the fabrication by other routes at high temperature can result in the absence of boron oxide phase and, thus, of a soluble phase that would allow the dispersion of NPs in aqueous media.

AFM measurements were carried out on the samples in order to study their morphology. As during the measurements they seemed quite hygroscopic and at the view of the surface chemical analysis, we decided to make an additional experiment. The samples were usually measured by AFM just after removal from the UHV chamber and then stored in vacuum. Figure 5a displays the typical morphology of spherical nanoparticles on a Si substrate of the *as deposited* sample in these conditions. The deposit was left in air for two months and then measured again. As can be seen in figure 5b, a different morphology was observed with new features surrounding the NPs that resemble to water bottlenecks caused by air humidity in contact with a hygroscopic material. A special tip for high resolution was used in these measurements³¹ in order to resolve the new structures that appeared in the sample. Then, a N_2 flux was introduced during the measurement to remove the adsorbed humidity. However the resulting morphology (figure 5c) was the same as before the N_2 flux exposure (figure 5b). Longer exposure times to the atmosphere induce higher water adsorption. As an example, figure 5d presents an image of the same sample after 6 months in air. As can be observed, the NPs appeared more blurred due to this higher water uptake. The goodness of the tip was double checked with other samples during the whole experiment to be sure that this surface morphology observed was not caused by a damaged tip.

The deposit was then heated progressively at increasing temperatures from 60°C to 100°C for 1 h in an attempt to remove any remaining water in the system. The morphology of the sample presented no change in any case (figure 5e-h). Therefore, the modification of the sample morphology observed after a storage period in air could be initially caused by humidity of the atmosphere that surrounds the hygroscopic NPs. This humidity trapped around the NPs might generate certain boron oxide dissolution, which could explain the retained morphology even after heating the sample at 100°C. At this temperature any water adsorbed is removed, but the boron oxide phase dissolved in this water surrounding the NPs remained, retaining the morphology.

Thus, dissolution of the boron oxide phase of these NPs was proven. In the following section where the NPs will be dispersed in solution, the NPs will then present a structure with a Fe⁰ core surrounded by a first shell mainly composed by iron oxides and hydroxides, with a small contribution of some remaining boron (oxy)nitride. Evidences of PEG attachment on the NPs forming a second shell were detected through the increase of the C content in the system, the apparition of a new component in the O 1s XPS core level and the characteristic PEG bands in the Raman spectra.

Dispersed NPs for *in vitro* MRI contrast agent applications

Once proven the PEG functionalization of *Fe-B(O-N)* NPs deposited on substrates, in this section we present the dispersion of *Fe-B(O-N)* NPs in aqueous media (*dispersed Fe-B(O-N) NPs* and *dispersed PEG-Fe-B(O-N) NPs*) and functionalization with PEG in one step. The resulting functionalized NPs are also tested for biomedical applications. We would like to point out that, during dispersion, no agglomeration of NPs was observed. The absence of precipitates and the change of the colour solution were indicative of a good colloidal stability as will be shown later.

Surface charge characterization: Zeta Potential—Variations in surface charge of dispersed NPs were investigated by means of zeta potential measurements as a way to evaluate the effectiveness of the functionalization process (figure 6). The *dispersed NPs* presented a charge close to -25 mV, while *dispersed PEG NPs* presented a positive potential close to 9 mV. This decrease in the net surface charge evidenced the presence of hydrophilic PEG attached on the NPs surface when dispersed in aqueous media^{32,33} and, therefore, an effective functionalization of the NPs.

Structural characterization: UV-Vis—UV-Vis analysis was carried out to investigate changes in surface chemical structure of dispersed NPs after PEG functionalization (see figure 7). The absorption spectra of *dispersed Fe-B(O-N) NPs* and *dispersed PEG-Fe-B(O-N) NPs* were recorded over the wavenumber range of 200 - 900 nm. A broad structure was observed in both spectra, in the range 250-467 nm, which is characteristic of iron oxides (magnetite, maghemite and hematite NPs)³⁴. A detailed analysis of figure 7 revealed that PEG incorporation to the *dispersed Fe-B(O-N) NPs* produced a significant increase in the absorbance slope on the 230 nm region (see inset of figure 7) as well as general enhancement of absorption signal.

Even if the higher absorbance of *dispersed PEG-Fe-B(O-N)NPs* spectra could be understood by the contribution of the PEG tail, other effects like the contribution of Fe^0 to the absorbance signal cannot be ruled out. For small particles of metallic iron, the absorption in the UV-Vis range presents a steep rise in absorption at very low wavelengths, and decreases gradually in the visible range, being away from zero at 900 nm³⁵. Although it cannot be established an univocal comparison, in-depth XPS analysis conducted on the samples revealed a larger Fe^0 content on the *PEG-Fe-B(O-N) NPs*.

Biomedical applications: MRI contrast agent—To assess the contrast dependence of Fe-B(O-N) NPs with PEG functionalization, differences between *dispersed Fe-B(O-N)* and *dispersed PEG-Fe-B(O-N) NPs* were evaluated. As we previously mentioned, dispersion of NPs in aqueous solution results in a colloidal stable solution as can be observed on top of figure 8. Darker images were observed in the samples containing the NPs in comparison with the control one indicating a negative contrast, in agreement with the literature³⁶. This reduction of T_2 signal compared to water control was 61.6% on *dispersed Fe-B(O-N) NPs* and 39.9% on the *dispersed PEG-Fe-B(O-N) NPs* solution. The difference between both NPs solutions could be understood on the basis of PEG coating. PEG probably reduces the access of water molecules to the magnetic core.

The transverse relaxivity (r_2) was also determined before and after PEG functionalization to evaluate the potential use of these NPs as MRI contrast agents. The r_2 relaxivity was found to be 2.5 larger in the case of *dispersed Fe-B(O-N) NPs* ($35 \pm 3 \text{ mM}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$) than in *dispersed PEG-Fe-B(O-N) NPs* ($15 \pm 3 \text{ mM}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$). This reduction after PEG functionalization is also related to the already mentioned decrease of M_S ³⁶.

Up to now SPIONs have been widely studied for their use as MRI contrast agents³⁷. However, there is a need for other NPs, especially those with different biodistribution, longer circulation times or positive contrast. Therefore it is worth considering new fabrication methods and NPs compositions. The alternative proposed here consists in the fabrication of SPMNPs formed by a metallic Fe^0 core with increased M_S , surrounded by an oxide shell. From previous studies we know that the superparamagnetic size of the NPs studied in this work is close to 3 nm¹⁶. A relaxivity of $75 \text{ mM}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ was reported for iron oxide NPs of 4 nm³⁸, a larger value than the one reported here using lower magnetic fields. Boron nitride nanotubes were also investigated as T_2 contrast agents with Fe NPs attached to one end as residue of the solid state preparation procedure. In that case, the Fe size was much bigger than in our case (20 nm) and also the observed contrast³⁹.

Nevertheless, the comparison of the values presented here with those reported in the literature is not straightforward as these experiments are usually conducted at 1.5 T or 3 T⁴⁰. In this paper we presented a new route for the fabrication of NPs with a metallic core surrounded by an oxide shell that can be dispersed and functionalized with PEG. Note that the fabrication method proposed here allows the tuning of the core size and, thus, offers the possibility of fabricating NPs with bigger metallic cores that will lead to higher M_S with improved properties for their use in biomedicine.

Conclusions

We reported the fabrication of Fe-B(O-N) NPs by a physical method using a gas aggregation source in UHV. The NPs were dispersed in aqueous media and further functionalized with PEG in one step as an attempt to study the feasibility of this technique as an alternative method to fabricate NPs for biomedical applications. The results presented here show that this procedure opens a new route for the fabrication of NPs with tailored structures that cannot be obtained by traditional routes. This paper proves how, through the use of boron, the dispersion process of the multilayer of NPs in aqueous media is facilitated. Boron is present as boron oxides and oxynitrides forming a shell on the NPs. The solubility of the boron oxide phase in aqueous media allows the correct dispersion of NPs from the multilayer fabricated and their functionalization with PEG, which forms a second shell on the NPs that makes them biocompatible. The studies carried out on these NPs functionalized with PEG to check their properties as contrast agents evidenced a clear T_2 attenuation in pre-clinical MRI conditions, which makes this fabrication route promising for the synthesis of new NPS for further studies.

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PEG structure: $\text{H}-(\text{O}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2)_n-\text{OH}$

Figure 1. Schematic representation of PEG functionalization of the NPs deposited on Si substrates (a) and dispersed in solution (b).

Figure 2. Comparative XPS core level spectra of as deposited (top) and as functionalized (bottom) *Fe-B(O-N)* NPs (a) Fe 2p; (b) B 1s; (c) N 1s; (d) O 1s.

Figure 3. Depth profile XPS analysis of *as functionalized Fe-B(O-N) NPs*. The dashed lines represent the C and B evolution of *as deposited Fe-B(O-N) NPs*¹⁶ for comparison purposes.

Figure 4. Comparative Raman spectra of the silicon substrate (a), the *as deposited* (b) and *as functionalized Fe-B(O-N) NPs* (c). The signatures of the main iron and boron oxides and hydroxides are included for the correct interpretation of the spectra.

Figure 5.

AFM images of *Fe-B(O-N)* NPs deposited on a Si(100) substrate (a) as fabricated; (b) after two months in air; (c) the same as (b) with a N₂ flux; after six months in air (d) at RT and after heating the sample at (e) 60 °C, (f) 75 °C, (g) 80 °C and (h) 100°C for one hour.

Figure 6.
Zeta potential of dispersed Fe-B(O-N) NPs and dispersed PEG-Fe-B(O-N) NPs.

Figure 7. UV-Vis spectra of dispersed Fe-B(O-N) and dispersed PEG-Fe-B(O-N) NPs. Inset: detail of the curve and difference between both.

Figure 8.

T_2 -weighted magnetic resonance imaging at 7 T comparing the T_2 contrast (darkening) in time from ultrapure deionized water, dispersed Fe-B(O-N) NPs and dispersed PEG-Fe-B(O-N) NPs with concentration of 0.30 mM.